

DIAGNOSTIC OF URBAN FLOODING IN KISUMU

Report 2026

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Executive Summary

The Space4All project develops action-oriented urban flood assessments to support decision-making in African cities. Since 2024, it has been implemented in six cities, including Kisumu, Kenya. While flood impacts are widely reported, spatial evidence remains limited. This report addresses this gap by providing a city-wide flood exposure map, validated with local stakeholders, highlighting affected areas and recommending urban adaptation strategies.

Results show that flooding affects 40% of the city. However, exposure is unevenly distributed, highly concentrated in populated deprived districts, including Manyatta, Nyalenda and Kolwa Central. These areas face recurring impacts, including damage to housing, disrupted livelihoods, disease outbreaks, and pressure on critical services.

Participatory activities with city authorities, local academia, civil society organizations and residents were essential to validate the findings, identify local drivers of flooding, foster inclusion and knowledge production. They revealed that models often underestimate exposure in deprived areas, particularly due to limitations in representing dense complex layout and local drainage issues. Overall, actual flood exposure is likely higher on the ground, underscoring the need for targeted risk reduction and infrastructure investment.

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1 Introduction

In February 2025, the Space4All team worked closely with residents from two different DUAs to map flood hotspots at community level and with local authorities and NGOs to map flood hotspots at city level. The team implemented and locally validated a state-of-the-art fast flood model, while incorporating local perspectives. In May 2025, hundreds of families evacuated their homes due to floods. Red Cross estimated that over 1400 households were affected, highlighting the dramatic effects of urban floods and the pressing need for spatially explicit, locally relevant flood information¹.

The project generated a high-resolution flood map at city level and a flood exposure map by overlaying the hazard map with global population dataset. The fieldwork created space for dialogue about flood impacts and underlying vulnerabilities of the life of the residents.

Project context

Kisumu, located on the shores of Lake Victoria, is the fifth largest city in Kenya with a little under 397,000 inhabitants. The city is vibrant with a key location as a strategic transportation hub between Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania. In the 90s, the city followed the national economic decline while experiencing continued urban growth, due to migration into and out major cities, resulting in urban poverty and population living in informal settlements (UN-Habitat, 2006). In 2009, in Kisumu had the highest national proportion of people living in informal settlements, almost half of all urban population (UNFPA, 2013). These settlements, located in lake-belt zones, have different settings in terms of extension, stage of development and density, but also similarities, in terms of location in lake-belt zones and deprived infrastructure conditions (Othoo et al., 2021). Among the districts known to be subject to flood impacts, Manyatta B, Nyalenda were selected for in-depth engagement considering Stream Power Index analysis, highlighting the most critical water accumulation points (Oliveira et al., 2025). In 2006, *Manyatta B* had over 21,000 people with a density estimated over 6,000 people/km², while *Nyalenda*,

¹ <https://www.capitalfm.co.ke/news/2025/05/several-families-left-homeless-after-heavy-rains-in-kisumu-homa-bay/>

combining settlements called Nyalenda A and B, had nearly 50,000 people with similar density (UN-Habitat, 2006). Together, these settlements account for 12km². Today a few portions of these settlements are targeted to planned urban development, but still large portion is neglected of public investment, Figure 1 illustrates the location of the city and communities involved.

Figure 1 -Study area and selected communities. The informal settlements data is available at <https://slumap.ulb.be/>.

Even though these deprived settlements are known to be the most affected areas, urban flood risk governance remains constrained within local government bodies, whose financial and human capacity are limited. The lack of spatial contextualized data on flood exposure and vulnerabilities constraint to effective flood mitigation and adaptation strategies. Flood maps at city scale are rare and mostly only use terrain data, not considering precipitation and urban local factors. Since no spatially explicit assessment is made available at city level, reference data is also lacking. To bridge the lack of contextualization, limited local engagement and local knowledge, we actively involve the residents of deprived areas and city actors. In that way, we mobilize wider insights, support inclusivity and co-produce methodologies and data to support integrated flood risk management.

With this in mind, this project aims:

- I. To actively engage local stakeholders in the research process.
- II. To understand flood vulnerability at community-level.
- III. To map flood exposure at city-level.

Understanding risk

The concept of risk plays a central role in flood assessments, particularly in the context of climate changes impacts. The IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report (AR6) defines disaster risk as the potential for adverse consequences on lives, livelihoods, ecosystems, and infrastructure due to climate-related hazards. Disaster risk arises from the interplay between three components: hazard, exposure, and vulnerability.

Figure 2- IPCC Disaster risk framework (Sixth Assessment Report).

A hazard is defined as the physical event or phenomenon that could potentially cause harm. In the case of urban flooding in Kisumu, heavy rainfall, exacerbated by climate change, serves as a primary hazard. The city's position is on the shores of Victoria Lake, covered by wetlands and limited natural drainage. The lake backflow is also experienced by the communities close to the borders too, in addition to artificial floods from poor sanitation infrastructure (Simiyu et al., 2019). Exposure refers to the presence of people, assets, or ecosystems in areas that are subject to hazards. In Kisumu, the low-lying configuration of the city exposes many areas to floods. Vulnerability is the predisposition of exposed elements to be adversely affected when impacted by hazards. Vulnerability is shaped by a range of factors, reflecting socio-economic, infrastructure and governance conditions that may exacerbate risks.

Measuring these concepts and analyzing their interaction with the human and environmental factors is not an easy task. It requires a lot of (spatial) information whose acquisition can also be challenge. In this report, we focus on mapping flood hazard and exposure in Kisumu, assessing spatial patterns and quantifying exposed areas, aside from identifying flood impacts and underlying vulnerabilities.

2 Methodology

The Space4All project follows a participatory data-driven approach. The research involved two main processes: (i) flood hazard and exposure estimation; (ii) citizen science methods, including local workshops, capacity building, participatory survey and transect walks). The next sections detail each part of the research process, as well as limitations of the methodological approach.

2.1. Flood hazard and exposure mapping

This section describes the methodology of the flood hazard modelling and exposure assessment. As the first step, a historical inspection was conducted, to verify past flood events reported in online media sources. An extensive accuracy check through the respective years was conducted, websites were screened, and official documents were collected to confirm the exact dates, duration of flood events and reported impacts. No spatial data on floods at city scale was found for reference, only at national level.

Based on this gap, FastFlood simulation model was employed to map flood extent and depth in Kisumu. The web-application was selected due to (i) the low-cost and user-friendliness of the platform, increasing future replicability of the method; (ii) the lower computational demands, when compared to traditional hydraulic models, allowing computation of large catchment areas in a few minutes; (iii) the open availability of global data repositories within the platform, reducing processing time (Van den Bout et al., 2022).

The model requires input datasets representing rainfall events (duration and intensity), elevation, terrain and infiltration. Datasets were downloaded already for the repository, aside from rainfall information that was acquired from Trans-African

Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO)². The institute provides daily and hourly precipitation data for two measurement stations in Kisumu region in a time series from January 2019 to January 2024. Table 1 describes the datasets used, detailing the properties and source.

Table 1 - Input datasets of FastFlood modelling.

Data	Source	Properties	Link
Rainfall	Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO)	Daily precipitation – no spatial resolution	https://tahmo.org/
Terrain	Copernicus GLO-30 DEM	Resolution: 40m	Earth Engine Catalog
Land use	Copernicus WorldCover	Resolution: 10m / 2021	ESA WorldCover 2021
Infiltration	SOILGRIDS (ISRIC)	Resolution: 250m / 2020	SoilGrids — global gridded soil information ISRIC

The model experiments were assessed visually and considering the lack of reference data, the computational time and further usability of the flood model, calibration was reduced to the minimum. Formal validation of the mapped flood hazard output was conducted qualitatively and quantitatively, both through citizen science methodologies during fieldwork that are explained in the subsequent section.

After local validation, the flood hazard map was overlaid with the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL)³, chosen based on its global consistency, suitable for cross-city comparison. to map flood exposure in built-up areas. A grid cell is classified as exposed when the simulated flood depth exceeds 10cm depth (natural break of the dataset and in accordance with international benchmarks) and when some part of the cell is built-up. We used the following thresholds to categorize the different built-up categories: Low exposure (up to 20% built up), Moderate exposure (up to 50% built up), High exposure (up to 100% built up). In the analysis, the degree

² <https://portal.tahmo.org/login>

³ The GHSL data can be found here <https://human-settlement.emergency.copernicus.eu/download.php?ds=bu>, by selecting the GHS-BUILT-S 2025 product, resolution: 100m, coordinate system: Mollweide, classification: Total RES+NRES

of exposure changes depending on the density of built-up structures, that is, the denser an area is, the more exposed people and structures are, thus more at risk.

2.2. Citizen science

Different stakeholders were actively engaged in the process, ensuring the analysis is faithful to the lived realities and fostering dialogue and awareness about the local flood issues. Through local partners in Kisumu, key stakeholders were connected considering who would benefit from the project. At city level, city authorities, local NGO actors and academics were contacted to participate in local workshops. At community level, residents from Manyatta B and Nyalenda A were contacted through local leaders to join workshops, training sessions, participatory surveys and transect walks. Table 2 describes the stakeholders involved in this process.

Table 2 - Stakeholders involved in the project.

Category	Stakeholders Involved	Activities
Community members	Residents from two communities	Community-level workshops, mapping surveys, transect walks
Civil Society Institutions	SDI Kenya, Organization for Nature Conservation (ORNACO)	City-level workshop
Government Agencies	Kisumu City Council	City-level workshop
Research Institutions	Maseno University	City-level workshop

Four citizen science approaches were conducted in Kisumu for 10 days in January 2025: local workshops at community and city-level, capacity building, mapping survey and transect walks.

In the workshops, 15 participants were invited to map and assess where flood events happen, collectively evaluate the results of the simulated flood map and identified the flood vulnerability factors in the communities. The selection of participants ensured participant diversity concerning their age, gender and

community roles. In total, 40 people joined, 15 in each community-level and 10 at city-level workshop.

The workshops were structured as a group activity that lasted 90 minutes. Using marker pens, pins and sticky notes, the participants marked areas that were correctly assigned as (recurrently) flooded and areas that should be marked as flooded and were not. They pinpointed previous flood events on the map, describing impacts on the neighborhoods. The groups presented their results in plenary and discussed validation procedures, indicating high agreement between them (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Photographs of workshops in Kisumu. Left in Nyalenda and right in Manyatta (Jan, 2025).

Eight DUA residents (4 in each community) were trained to use Google My Maps tool and to conduct a mapping survey of flood observation points from past flood events. The tutorial from Data4HumanRights⁴ was adapted as baseline and the survey content was discussed with participants, including information on flood event dates, water depth and impacts. They also developed the route among their pairs and tested with a dummy file and established further communication channel for the actual survey day and possible issues. A few days later, the eight trained residents conducted the mapping survey in their own communities. In total, 95 flood observation points were mapped by them. After fieldwork, the flood observation points collected using Google My Maps were used to validate the flood model. The non-numeric flood depth information collected by the community

⁴ <https://www.data4humanrights.net/training-materials/5-2-google-maps-app>

members (ankle, knee, waist and above-the-head level) was converted into numeric thresholds according to Table 3.

Table 3 – Categories of flood depth for quantitative evaluation of the flood model at community level.

Flood depth category	Ankle-height	Knee-height	Waist-height	Head-height
Numeric conversion	Up to 15 cm	Between 15 and 50 cm	Between 50 and 100cm	Above 100cm

Additionally, transect walks, complementary ethnographic activity, were conducted with community members from Manyatta B. The route was approved together with local leaders, considering coverage of main flood spots. The project team observed through photographs previous flood depth markings and listened to participants' narratives about critical issues and possible factors.

2.3. Limitations

A few methodological limitations should be considered: (1) the data collectors using Google My Maps which can only map flood points along riverbanks and streets. It introduces a bias for validation; (2) the number of flood observation points collected was not significant for a quantitative analysis, only representative; (3) it is possible that the results would be different if the local discharge behaviors could be analyzed. This would require local data collection campaigns to determine the base discharge conditions.

3 Results

The analysis shows the flood patterns in Kisumu is widespread but exposure and its impacts are not evenly distributed across the city. The most exposed areas are located in the eastern part of the city, particularly in deprived settlements, such as Manyatta, Nylenda and Kolwa (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Flood Exposure map.

The simulated flood map for the event of May 13th, 2021 estimates that about 40% of the city is flood-prone to flood waters. However, the level of impact depends on whether people, buildings and infrastructure are present in these areas. When

taking this into account, 22.5% of the city (47.8km²) is moderately exposed to floods, and 3.5% (7.6km²) is highly exposed. This result is consistent with the discussions reported during local workshops, where participants described major flood impacts in deprived communities, including disease outbreak, property destruction, displacement, loss of livelihoods and, in some cases, loss of lives.

At the district level, there are important differences (Table 4). For example, Market Milimani has over 60% of its area prone to flooding. Yet, because much of this area is not built-up (covered with many green areas), only about 3% of the territory is actually exposed to flood impacts. In contrast, the Manyata B, Nyalenda A and Kolwa Central show much higher levels of flood exposure, 20%, 12% and 11% of their areas affected, respectively. Together, these three districts account for about half of the total exposed area (3.8km²) in the city, which are mostly composed by deprived (informal) communities that face severe flood impacts on a regular basis. The map also shows the exposure of important public services, such as school and health facilities, in these settlements. In the workshops, residents reported that flooding often disrupts school attendance, damages infrastructure and overwhelms the public health system with disease outbreaks.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of flood proneness and flood exposure in Kisumu grouped per district.

District	Area (Km ²)	Flood-prone area (Km ²)	Flood-prone area (%)	Built-up area (%)	Built-up flood prone area (m ²)	Built-up flood prone area (%)
Market Milimani	27.05	18.19	67%	20%	142500	3%
South West Kisumu	124.48	72.21	58%	37%	235000	1%
Kolwa East	73.14	40.3	55%	46%	790000	2%
Nyalenda B	18.06	9.41	52%	28%	450000	9%
Central Kisumu	59.92	30.41	51%	42%	462500	2%
Kolwa Central	47.92	24.29	51%	51%	2685000	11%
Nyalenda 'A'	3.51	1.10	31%	94%	397500	12%
Manyatta 'B'	4.28	1.24	29%	94%	792500	20%
Migosi	1.13	0.25	22%	92%	57500	6%
Railways	16.03	3.46	22%	77%	655000	5%
Kajulu	36.30	4.24	12%	84%	270000	1%
West Kisumu	59.37	6.89	12%	78%	140000	0%
North West Kisumu	36.08	3.18	9%	83%	97500	0%
Kisumu North	32.53	2.02	6%	86%	67500	0%
Kondele	2.11	0.03	1%	100%	12500	1%
Shaurimoyo Kaloleni	3.94	0.06	1%	99%	30000	1%

In Kolwa Central, we also inspected the low-built up areas along the Nyamasaria river identified as highly flood-prone but appear only as moderately exposed in the map, due to lower building density. This does not mean that impacts are lower, but simply that exposure classification is relative: areas with fewer buildings are shown as less exposed compared to dense settlements. Residents reported significant impacts on livelihoods along the river including soil erosion and livestock losses. This highlights that areas classified as moderately exposed can still experience severe consequences, and results should therefore be interpreted with this in mind.

Validation through workshops and field observations helped identify important gaps in the flood model. First, in very dense informal settlements, the global built-up dataset (GHSL) tends to underestimate how built-up these areas actually are, mainly due to their complex and compact layout. As a result, some highly exposed spots are likely underrepresented in the analysis, that is, the actual exposure on the ground may be higher than what the map represents. Second, residents spotted several cases of artificial floods, caused by poor sanitation and blocked drainage systems, which are not captured by the flood model at this level of detail, but play an important role increasing flood impacts locally.

Transect walks confirmed that local conditions are highly variable, even within the same settlement (Figure 5). We observed different building materials, construction types, as well as formal and informal drainage systems (solid construction work along with improvised self-made drainage channels). Several blocked bottlenecks of the drainage systems due to solid waste. These factors play a major role in how flooding occurs and how the residents experience the impacts at community level.

Figure 5: Photos taken during transect walks in Manyatta B (Jan, 2025).

4 Key learnings

This report provides a foundation for informed strategic planning to strengthen equitable disaster risk policies in Kisumu. The analysis reveals:

Flood exposure is unevenly distributed across the city. While flooding affects large areas of Kisumu, the highest levels of exposure are concentrated in densely populated informal settlements, particularly in the eastern part of the city.

Critical services are at risk. Educational and health facilities located in flood-prone areas are regularly disrupted. This not only affects infrastructure but also had wider social consequences, including reduced access to healthcare and education, aside from increased pressure on already strained public services.

Moderate exposure does not mean low impact. Low built-up areas also experience serious impacts, particularly on livelihoods. Exposure levels should therefore be interpreted as relative, not absolute.

Local conditions influence flood impacts. Artificial flood factors such as blocked drainage, inadequate waste disposal and poor sanitation can worsen flooding. The results confirm that the built-up characteristics of deprived settlements highly influence their flood exposure, which is stressed by both city and community actors.

Flood exposure is likely underestimated in some areas. Due to global data and model limitations, artificial flood factors cannot be well captured and built-up density is underrepresented in highly dense settings. In practice, this suggests that the conditions on the ground are likely worse than what is shown in the maps.

Citizen science is essential for contextual understanding of flood risk. **Engagement with residents helped identify** model uncertainties, validate results and uncover local drivers of flooding. While the city-level stakeholders highlighted planning, governance and cultural aspects, community members emphasized sanitation, building layout and livelihoods. This shows that flood exposure in Kisumu is shaped not only by water extent and depth, but also by infrastructure gaps, urban conditions and local practices. Addressing these challenges requires a combination of targeted investments and strong community engagement.

5 Recommendations

Resilient urban planning requires context-specific strategies that integrate both city planning and local knowledge. As climate change intensifies flood risks, flood management must become a central component of urban development. In informal areas, where data and engagement are often limited, working closely with communities is key to understanding local realities and co-developing effective solutions. Based on this, we propose the following priorities for action:

CITY-LEVEL ACTION

- Prioritize high-exposure settlements for targeted flood risk reduction measures
- Assess and protect critical infrastructure
- Invest in upgrading sanitation systems
- Use participatory approaches as standard practice

COMMUNITY-LEVEL ACTION

- Improve emergency response by developing local response plans and training community members
- Support awareness campaigns using simplified versions of the outputs
- Support livelihood resilience of households affected by floods

DATA-LEVEL ACTION

- Refine the outputs by using local mapping, building footprints and data on artificial flood factors
- Institutionally integrate community knowledge into model improvements
- Take outputs as relative indicators of risk not absolute truths

6 Outlook and future research

This work provides a strong foundation for continued collaboration and practical application. Space4All project places strong emphasis on information outreach, through accessible outputs, such as simplified maps and infographics tailored to different stakeholders. There is also opportunity to train institutional staff to use the FastFlood model, supporting long-term capacity. Interested partners are encouraged to contact the project team to explore reduced-cost options.

Improving local data collection also remains essential. Investing in discharge measurements and flood observation – particularly with community involvement – can enhance the model accuracy and relevance, aside from supporting ongoing community awareness campaigns.

The next research phase will focus on understanding links between flood impacts and underlying local vulnerabilities. This builds on the co-designed impact chains developed during the workshops and aims to better connect flood processes and local urban dynamics, supporting more targeted and equitable solutions.

This image was AI-generated.

7 Acknowledgements

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